

Theoretical Studies on the Intercalation of Actinomycin between Nucleic Acid Base Pairs

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Energies associated with the actinomycin chromophore sandwiched between base pairs of dinucleotide model systems have been calculated using classical potential functions. The energy values are partitioned into contributions from electrostatic, polarisation, dispersion and repulsion terms. The results indicate that contributions from dispersion term dominate the calculated energy values. The energy is minimised by varying rotational angle of drug moiety about helix axis and translation along the X, Y and Z axis relative to the base pairs. The helical angle between two base pairs is also varied and the optimised values are found to lie in the range -7° to -8° for all model systems. The stacked geometries of drug chromophore intercalated between base pairs corresponding to the minimum energy, have been obtained. The effect of base sequence on stacking energy, and unwinding angle have been discussed.

Cancer chemotherapy relies heavily on the inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis as a means of selective discrimination against fast growing tumor cells. Actinomycin D belongs to a well known class of antibiotics isolated from *Streptomyces parvulus*. It came into medical prominence as it proved to be extremely effective in certain kinds of cancer, viz. chlorocarcinoma, even though its high toxicity has precluded wider clinical use. Efforts have been made to understand its chemistry and biological action in inhibiting DNA directed RNA synthesis and elongation of growing RNA chains, and to reduce its toxicity while maintaining the pharmacological activity. The mechanism of action is mainly attributed to intercalation¹, that is, the insertion of its planar chromophore between adjacent base pairs in a DNA duplex, with an increase in the base pair separation. Since the hypothesis of intercalation was proposed², experimental results by sedimentation, viscosity, X-ray diffraction and nmr techniques³⁻¹² have thrown valuable light on the nature of drug nucleotide interaction.

In order to look into the energetics of intercalation, systematic theoretical methods have been applied to simplified model systems. On the basis of multipole interactions¹³, it has been shown that the intercalation of ethidium results in change in enthalpy by -12.3 to -24.0 kcal mol⁻¹ with a

preference for pyr (3'-5') pur base sequence. The specificity is primarily controlled by the energy required to open the helix to accommodate intercalator. Similar specificity has also been observed¹⁴ by calculating energy changes on varying all torsional angles and changing sugar pucker at the intercalation site. Another approach to scan conformational space has shown¹⁵ that three regions of intercalation sites exist which can be characterised by the helical angle (α). Unwinding of DNA is accompanied by a change in the sugar pucker and a disjoint in helical axis of successive base pairs¹⁶. A separate investigation has shown¹⁷ that change in helical angle ($\Delta\alpha$) may range between -15° (unwinding) and $+16^\circ$ (winding). It has also been shown that optimum intercalation geometry for actinomycin may be realised¹⁸ without a change in sugar pucker and without introducing specific kinks. Further d-5'-C-G-3' step is more favourable than the d-5'-G-C-3' for stretching and unwinding of B DNA, while the reverse is true for Z DNA, and the existence of O1' endo sugar conformation is preferred for intercalation.

Since the anticancerous action of actinomycin has been attributed to intercalation, it is worth examining the role of intermolecular interaction energy due to stacking of drug chromophore between the base pairs, its base sequence specificity, relation to unwinding angle and the

stacking patterns obtained for various base pair sequences corresponding to the optimised energy values. With this goal, we have carried out energy calculations due to stacking with various unwinding angles. Since our interest is focussed on stacking energy only, the calculations have been restricted to the planar part of the drug molecule sandwiched between two base pairs. The energy required for opening the helix to generate intercalation site has been taken from the literature^{13,15}, in order to obtain total change in energy following intercalation.

Computational methods

Interaction energy : The structure of nucleic acid bases and base pairs have been taken from the

results of single crystal X-ray diffraction studies¹⁹. The geometry of actinomycin ring has been adopted from X-ray studies reported in literature¹⁶. The charge distributions of these molecules have been calculated by the complete neglect of differential overlap (CNDO) method²⁰. For actinomycin, side-chains attached to chromophore were replaced by hydrogen atoms so that only the planar moiety of drug has been used for CNDO calculations. Partial charges and dipole moments thus obtained are given in Table 1.

Intermolecular interaction energy has been calculated as a sum of contributions from electrostatic (el), polarisation (pol), dispersion (disp) and repulsion (rep) interactions using classical

TABLE 1—PARTIAL CHARGES AND DIPOLE MOMENTS AT ATOMIC CENTRES OF ACTINOMYCIN CHROMOPHORE

Sl. no.	Atomic no.	Charge	Dipole moment (Debye)		
			DipX	DipY	DipZ
1.	8	-0.182	0.719	-1.136	0.000
2.	6	0.127	-0.287	0.009	0.000
3.	6	0.009	-0.022	-0.110	0.000
4.	6	-0.005	-0.084	-0.121	0.000
5.	6	0.014	-0.119	-0.018	0.002
6.	6	0.026	-0.021	0.085	-0.002
7.	6	0.064	-0.070	-0.077	-0.001
8.	7	0.133	-0.922	1.562	0.000
9.	6	0.103	0.063	0.009	0.001
10.	6	0.072	-0.089	0.065	0.003
11.	6	0.133	0.038	-0.156	-0.003
12.	6	0.228	-0.062	-0.072	0.000
13.	6	-0.078	0.150	-0.082	0.000
14.	6	0.164	0.166	0.072	0.000
15.	8	0.330	1.336	0.064	0.000
16.	7	-0.263	0.040	0.072	0.001
17.	6	0.244	0.180	0.078	-0.020
18.	6	0.233	-0.174	-0.146	0.020
19.	6	-0.014	0.084	-0.154	0.000
20.	6	0.000	0.133	-0.166	0.000
21.	8	-0.254	-1.318	0.077	-0.041
22.	8	-0.231	0.562	1.195	-0.041
23.	1	-0.039	0.000	0.000	0.000
24.	1	-0.044	0.000	0.000	0.000
25.	1	0.123	0.000	0.000	0.000
26.	1	0.126	0.000	0.000	0.000
27.	1	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000
28.	1	0.012	0.000	0.000	0.000

Table-1 (Contd.)

29.	1	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000
30.	1	0.015	0.000	0.000	0.000
31.	1	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.000
32.	1	0.015	0.000	0.000	0.000
33.	1	-0.039	0.000	0.000	0.000
34.	1	-0.004	0.000	0.000	0.000

potential functions (CPF). Such an approach has been widely used in the study of protein structures²¹, nucleic acid structures²², and drug nucleic acid interactions²³. We have used perturbation method using the simplified formulae of Clavarie²⁴, since the rigorous quantum mechanical approach requires large computer resources. Thus total interaction energy (E_{inter}) is a sum of electrostatic (E_{el}), polarisation (E_{pol}), dispersion (E_{disp}) and repulsion (E_{rep}) energies,

$$E_{inter} = E_{el} + E_{pol} + E_{disp} + E_{rep}$$

Simplified formulae of partitioned energy terms have been used as detailed elsewhere²⁵.

Minimum energy configuration : In order to find the minimum energy and thus, the most stable geometry of stacked molecules, the relative orientation of molecules is initialised as shown in Fig. 1. In the Cartesian coordinate system ($X Y Z$), the base pairs are held rigid such that the planar base ring is in the XY plane with the Z axis passing approximately through the centre of the base moiety. The two base pairs are initially oriented at an angle (α) of 36° with respect to each other. The drug chromophore is oriented parallel to XY plane and placed exactly in the middle of two base pairs. The distance between the base pairs is optimised by varying it from 6.0 to 6.8 Å in steps of 0.2 Å. The search for minimum energy configuration is then made by rotating the drug chromophore around the Z axis at an interval of 10° ($\Delta\theta$) and sliding it along X and Y axis for each orientation by a displacement of 0.1 Å (Δx , Δy). Further refinement of rotation of chromophore about Z axis is done at an interval of 1° and interaction energy is calculated at each step. The global search for unwinding angle ($\Delta\alpha$), is carried out by varying it in the range -180° to $+180^\circ$ in steps of 20° and stacking energy is calculated for each step by optimising $\Delta\theta$, Δx , Δy

and Δz . Local refinement of unwinding angle is done in steps of 1° .

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the relative orientation of two base pairs (rings A and C) with actinomycin drug chromophore (ring B) intercalated between them

Results and Discussion

Intercalation is affected by insertion of a planar chromophore between base pairs with a simultane-

ous increase in the base pair separation to about 6.8 Å. The intercalated structure is stabilised by stacking interaction between the drug chromophore and the base pairs. Detailed calculations have been made to study stacking energy by sandwiching actinomycin chromophore between two base pairs. Fig. 2 shows the interaction energy due to stacking (E_{inter}) by positioning the actinomycin chromophore exactly midway between the two base pairs CG and

Fig. 2. Energy due to stacking interaction E_{inter} as a function of (a) rotational angle θ and displacement along X, Y and Z directions. The energy shows minima at rotational angles of 315° and 140° , which are approximately 180° apart. These two rotational angles presumably refer to the two positions of drugs in which the total overlap interaction with the nucleic acid base pairs is maximum. After further refinement of energy values in steps of 1° , the energy was minimum at 1.0 \AA and increase on increasing or decreasing Δx , that is, as the drug molecule moves away from the base pairs due to lesser extent of overlap. Same is observed on displacement of ring along the Y axis. The energy is found to be minimum at $z = 6.6 \text{ \AA}$. It increases rapidly on decreasing the distance below 6.6 \AA and rather gradually beyond 6.6 \AA . Such a result is consistent with the concept that the base pairs must reorganise by opening from their usual distance of

GC having a relative orientation of 27° , as a function of rotational angle θ and displacement along X, Y and Z directions. The energy shows minima at rotational angles of 315° and 140° , which are approximately 180° apart. These two rotational angles presumably refer to the two positions of drugs in which the total overlap interaction with the nucleic acid base pairs is maximum. After further refinement of energy values in steps of 1° , the energy was minimum at 1.0 \AA and increase on increasing or decreasing Δx , that is, as the drug molecule moves away from the base pairs due to lesser extent of overlap. Same is observed on displacement of ring along the Y axis. The energy is found to be minimum at $z = 6.6 \text{ \AA}$. It increases rapidly on decreasing the distance below 6.6 \AA and rather gradually beyond 6.6 \AA . Such a result is consistent with the concept that the base pairs must reorganise by opening from their usual distance of

3.4 \AA to about $6.6\text{--}6.8 \text{ \AA}$ in order to accommodate the drug moiety. Another example of stacking between CG and AT base pairs is also shown in Fig. 2. Similar results have been obtained for other model dinucleotide systems.

While opening the base pairs, a conformational adjustment takes place in the helix resulting in a change in angular disposition of base pairs on either side. A global search was made for the best unwinding angle for actinomycin, intercalating between different sets of base pairs. Fig. 3 shows the result of calculation for base pairs CG and GC. Minimum energy values are observed for three sets

Fig. 3. Global search for optimum unwinding angle, $\Delta\alpha$. The inset shows the variation in E_{inter} around the optimum unwinding angle for actinomycin chromophore intercalated between CG and GC base pairs.

of unwinding angle, i.e. -20° , -80° and 140° . Of the three values, the minimum at -80° and 140° are sterically forbidden in the presence of phosphate backbone and a large change in overlap angles may cause long range disorders in double stranded nucleic acids. Therefore, the configuration corresponding to an angle of -20° with a total potential energy of $-37.62 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ can be considered at the optimised minimum. The inset in Fig. 3 shows the results of further local refinement of unwinding angle in the range 0° to -20° in steps of 1° . The minimum at -7° with a total potential energy of $-36.72 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ corresponds to the optimised configuration. Similar behaviour was observed for other model systems

TABLE 2—PARTITIONING OF STACKING ENERGY E_{inter} VALUES (kcal mol^{-1}) OF STACKED COMPLEX OF ACTINOMYCIN CHROMOPHORE WITH DIFFERENT DINUCLEOTIDE MODEL SYSTEMS ALONG WITH THE OPTIMISED DISTANCE (\AA) BETWEEN BASE PAIRS AND UNWINDING ANGLE ($\Delta\alpha$)

System	Distance	E_{tot}	E_{el}	E_{pol}	E_{ddep}	E_{rep}	$\Delta\alpha$
CG ... GC	6.6	-36.72	-2.40	-3.87	-52.39	21.94	-7°
CG ... CG	6.4	-50.01	-13.39	-6.73	-60.89	31.00	-8°
CG ... AT	6.8	-41.54	-9.29	-3.99	-44.84	16.58	-8°
AT ... AT	6.4	-37.68	-8.40	-4.37	-48.20	23.29	-8°
AT ... TA	6.8	-35.61	-5.86	-2.74	-40.89	13.88	-8°
GC ... AT	6.6	-37.25	-4.53	-3.85	-52.31	23.44	-8°

Table 2 summarises the results of energy calculations along with optimised unwinding angle for other base pair systems. It is clearly seen that the optimised unwinding angle lies in the range -7° to -8°. Any specificity towards the type of base pair system is not apparent from the data. These values of $\Delta\alpha$ are lower than those reported in literature¹. The total energy value lies in the range -35 to -50 kcal mol^{-1} with binding being strong when actinomycin is intercalated between CG and CG base pairs. The predominant contribution to the total interaction energy comes from dispersion term which is greater than the total energy in all the complexes. The electrostatic and polarisation terms are much smaller and lesser than the repulsion terms. However, the relative trends in stacking energies, even though characterised by dominant contributions from the dispersion terms, cannot be explained by dispersion terms alone. The dispersion terms decrease in the order :

It is observed that dispersion terms are higher for the system containing two guanine bases. The electrostatic, polarisation and repulsion terms are

sensitive to the kind of atoms and their relative positions in the optimised conformations. The net energy values therefore show a trend of decreasing interaction between various base pair systems in the order :

Fig. 4. shows the overlap geometries of actinomycin chromophore stacked between two base pairs in the optimised configuration. These structures indicate the diverse nature of stacked geometries. The stacking pattern supports the selective bookmark hypothesis²⁶ which states that the nucleotide sequences can be recognised by the drug chromophore acting like bookmarks. The trend in the extent of overlap for different base pair systems does not follow the trend in values of minimum energies.

The energetics of intermolecular interaction of DNA with drugs can be understood by decomposing E_{total} into two components : (a) an energy of unwinding from B form to the intercalated form, $E_{\text{unwinding}}$; this is referred to as E_{CA} , energy for conformational adjustment by Ornstein and Rein¹³, as E_{open} , i.e. energy required

Fig. 4. Stacked geometries of the actinomycin ring intercalated between different model dinucleotide systems corresponding to minimum energies.

for opening the helix to accommodate drug chromophore by Miller and Pycior¹⁵ and as E_{unstack} by Chen *et al.*¹³, and (b) energy due to stacking of drug chromophore between the base pairs, E_{inter} .

The unwinding or opening of DNA helix is the first step in drug/ligand-DNA interactions and is essentially common to gene expression and replication. Though the extent of unwinding varies with the nature of the drug and the nucleic acid system, it invariably gives rise to an increase in energy. The extent of unwinding is measured as a

change in helical angle α , of bases from the standard B form and as the energy $E_{\text{unwinding}}$ involved in separating base pairs from a normal distance of 3.4 to 6.8 Å. It has been shown¹³ that typically 5'-3' d-TpA, d-CpG, d-CpA ($E_{\text{unwinding}} = 3-4 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) open more easily than d-GpC, d-ApT, etc. ($E_{\text{unwinding}} = 15-17 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$). It has also been shown¹⁵ that DNA opens to one of the three representative conformations of principle intercalation sites characterised by unwinding angle. Since the experimental unwinding angle is about

23° for actinomycin¹, site III B is the possible mode of intercalation. The corresponding values of $E_{\text{unwinding}}$ are listed in Table 3. We have calculated the change in energy due to stacking of actinomycin chromophore between the base pair sequences. This is attributed to induced dipole interaction between electron clouds of stacked rings. It has been shown that energy involved in change of conformation on intercalation of drug chromophore after the helix has opened, is small (being 10 kcal mol⁻¹) as compared to the total energy of intercalated form, i.e. 420 kcal mol⁻¹²³. Therefore, the assumption that the change in energy due to conformational variation on intercalation is small, is justified. Since the backbone has not been considered, 5'-3' d-GpC system is the same as 5'-3' d-CpG for the purpose of calculating E_{inter} .

The stacking energy shows base sequence dependence. The stability of intercalated complex decreases in the order :

It is well known that stacking decreases preferentially as : pur-pur > pur-pyr > pyr-pyr.

With drug intercalated between two base pairs it appears that the preference is as follows :

Energy due to unwinding is energetically unfavourable but the consequent input of energy due to intercalation, E_{inter} , overrides the helix opening, thereby stabilising the intermolecular interaction. Therefore the net energy change, E_{total} is given as $E_{\text{total}} = E_{\text{unwinding}} + E_{\text{inter}}$.

It may be noted that E_{inter} is dominated by the stacking interaction and is quite independent of backbone, whereas the $E_{\text{unwinding}}$ is largely a conformational adjustment to accommodate chromophore and hence depends on backbone conformation. We have used the values of $E_{\text{unwinding}}$ given in literature to calculate E_{total} . These values are tabulated in Table 3. It is clearly seen that E_{total} shows base sequence specificity which is same for calculations done by two different methods (Column 6 and 7 in Table 3). The total change in energy of a model dinucleotide system due to intercalation of actinomycin chromophore thus

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF $E_{\text{unwinding}}$, E_{CA} AND E_{open} (FROM LITERATURE), E_{inter} (PRESENT WORK) AND E_{total} IN (kcal mol⁻¹) ALONGWITH OBSERVED UNWINDING ANGLES (α , IN DEGREE) FOR ACTINOMYCIN INTERCALATED BETWEEN DIFFERENT DINUCLEOTIDE MODEL SYSTEMS

Sl. no	System	E_{CA}^*	E_{open}^{**}	E_{inter}	E_{total}	E_{total}	Unwinding angle
				Present work	using Col 3	using Col 4	
1.	AT	3.5	20.6	-35.61	-32.11	-15.01	-8
	TA						
2.	AT	2.7	22.5	-41.54	-38.84	-19.04	-8
	CG						
3.	GC	3.9	24.0	-36.72	-32.82	-12.72	-7
	CG						
4.	AT	5.0	27.9	-37.25	-32.25	-9.35	-8
	GC						
5.	GC	6.5	29.9	-50.01	-43.51	-20.11	-8
	GC						
6.	AT	12.2	31.0	-37.68	-25.48	-6.68	-8
	AT						
7.	TA	8.5	33.1	-37.25	-28.75	-4.15	-8
	CG						
8.	TA	16.7	39.1	-35.61	-18.91	-3.69	-8
	AT						

Table-3 (Contd.)

9.	TA ... GC	10.6	38.1	-41.54	-30.94	-19.04	-7
10.	CG ... GC	14.9	37.6	-36.72	-21.82	+0.88	-8
11.	CG ... CG	6.0	—	-50.01	—	-44.01	-8
12.	CG ... TA	6.9	—	-37.25	—	-30.35	-8
13.	GC ... TA	5.0	—	-41.54	—	-36.54	-8
14.	CG ... AT	12.7	—	-41.54	—	-28.84	-8
15.	TA ... TA	12.0	—	-37.68	—	-25.68	-8
16.	GC ... AT	11.0	—	-37.25	—	-26.25	-8

*From Ref. 13. **From Ref. 15.

shows the following base sequence specificity in the order of decreasing binding/interaction :

This apparently demonstrates that for GC base pair, homopolymers are preferred over alternating polymer that is, copolymer of poly(dC) and poly(dG) (sequence no. 5) will be preferred over poly(dGC) (sequence no. 3 or 10). The difference in total energy is about 7 to 17 kcal mol⁻¹. On the other hand, for AT base pair, alternating polymer is preferred over copolymer of poly(dA) and poly(dT). Further, as is known, it is easier to open a helix having 5'-3' pur-pur, e.g. d-CpG site than 5'-3' pur-pyr, e.g. d-GpC site for drugs^{13,15}. However, in actinomycin d-GpC site is preferred because E_{inter} overrides the effect of changes in backbone conformation. Since the intermolecular interaction involving side-chain of actinomycin is the dominant term and is determining factor for base sequence specificity, it may not be advisable to relate the observed

base sequence specificity (Table 3, column 7) to the data available in literature^{6,10,12,17,18,27}.

The energy required for unwinding the helix to accommodate drug chromophore varies over a range of 3-16 kcal mol⁻¹ (E_{CA}) and 20-30 kcal mol⁻¹ (E_{open}). The present investigations show that the energy due to stacking of drug between base pair varies in a narrow range of -35 to -41 kcal mol⁻¹ (except for GC and GC base pairs where E_{inter} is -50 kcal mol⁻¹ for different model dinucleotide systems. The corresponding variation in unwinding angle is however small, being -7° to -8°. Also the value of unwinding angle is much lower than the value of -26° observed by X-ray and other investigations. Actinomycin has a large size aromatic ring and bulky side-chains which bind in minor groove resulting in change in sugar conformation²⁸ as well as base pair pairing scheme, that is, from Watson-Crick to Hoogsteen configuration¹². The present finding of $\Delta\alpha = -7$ to -8° is therefore understandable, since side-chains of actinomycin have not been considered for intermolecular energy calculation. Nevertheless, our results clearly demonstrate that neither the intermolecular stacking energy dominated by dispersion energy terms, nor the unwinding angle are dependent on the base sequence.

It is significant to note that considering stacking energy alone, the energetically most favoured conformation should correspond to configuration in which actinomycin ring has a maximum overlaps with the base pairs. Our results (Fig. 4) show that drug chromophore overlaps in an orientation parallel to the base pairs for model dinucleotide systems involving two CG and one CG one AT base pair system. These stacking patterns involve maximum overlap of aromatic rings resulting in minimum stacking energy. The observed geometries are consistent with that observed for intercalation of actinomycin between d-CG and d-ATGCAT oligonucleotide^{10,16,27} and those predicted by previous theoretical investigations²⁹. The corresponding overlap geometry for actinomycin ring stacked between two AT base pairs is however not parallel to base pairs (Fig. 4). Since actinomycin binds preferentially to nucleotides containing guanine residue, there are no experimental data available for AT nucleotide sequences.

Stacking interaction manifests itself in the form of change in chemical shift of ring protons of actinomycin and nonexchangeable protons of bases of nucleic acid in the nmr spectra of drug-nucleic acid complexes. The base protons of nucleic acids shift upfield or downfield due to the difference in ring current effect or neighbouring base pair and actinomycin ring. On the other hand, H7, H8, 4-CH₃ and 6-CH₃ protons of actinomycin are expected to shift upfield in complexed form as compared to the free drug. Typically large upfield shifts ~ 0.9 to 1.1 ppm have been observed for H7 protons on complexation with d-ATGCAT, d-GpC and d-GMP^{4,12,30}. The H8, 4-CH₃ and 6-CH₃ protons shift upfield by 0.4 to 0.7, 0.4–0.6 and 0.5 to 0.6 ppm respectively. Crystal structure of actinomycin-d-CpG complex also supports the large upfield shifts as a result of stacking²⁷. Our results on stacking energy calculation also predict that, for intercalation involving GC base pair, H7 and H8 will experience large upfield shifts ~1 ppm and are thus consistent with experimental results. The stacking with AT base pairs will result in opposite effect as H7 and H8 protons are nearly outside the effective range of ring currents due to base pairs, and 4-CH₃, 6-CH₃ protons are expected to shift

upfield by large amounts ~1 ppm. The present investigations on stacking energy calculations, the unwinding angle and overlap geometries of complexes with various model systems serve as guideline for understanding drug nucleic acid interactions. Such studies may help in developing a rational approach to engineering of anticancerous, antileukemic drugs which bind by stacking/intercalation to DNA.

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